

Multifunctional Heteropentalenes: From Synthesis to Optoelectronic Applications

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Electronic supporting information

The DFT computation

Geometry optimizations and energies of HOMO-LUMO orbitals were computed via PBE0/6-31(d) method (for heavy atoms (Se and Te atoms SDD was applied) by using The Gaussian 03¹ quantum mechanical package.

References:

¹ Frisch, M. J.; Trucks, G. W.; Schlegel, H. B.; Scuseria, G. E.; Robb, M. A.; Cheeseman, J. R.; Montgomery, Jr., J. A.; Vreven, T.; Kudin, K. N.; Burant, J. C.; Millam, J. M.; Iyengar, S. S.; Tomasi, J.; Barone, V.; Mennucci, B.; Cossi, M.; Scalmani, G.; Rega, N.; Petersson, G. A.; Nakatsuji, H.; Hada, M.; Ehara, M.; Toyota, K.; Fukuda, R.; Hasegawa, J.; Ishida, M.; Nakajima, T.; Honda, Y.; Kitao, O.; Nakai, H.; Klene, M.; Li, X.; Knox, J. E.; Hratchian, H. P.; Cross, J. B.; Bakken, V.; Adamo, C.; Jaramillo, J.; Gomperts, R.; Stratmann, R. E.; Yazyev, O.; Austin, A. J.; Cammi, R.; Pomelli, C.; Ochterski, J. W.; Ayala, P. Y.; Morokuma, K.; Voth, G. A.; Salvador, P.; Dannenberg, J. J.; Zakrzewski, V. G.; Dapprich, S.; Daniels, A. D.; Strain, M. C.; Farkas, O.; Malick, D. K.; Rabuck, A. D.; Raghavachari, K.; Foresman, J. B.; Ortiz, J. V.; Cui, Q.; Baboul, A. G.; Clifford, S.; Cioslowski, J.; Stefanov, B. B.; Liu, G.; Liashenko, A.; Piskorz, P.; Komaromi, I.; Martin, R. L.; Fox, D. J.; Keith, T.; Al-Laham, M. A.; Peng, C. Y.; Nanayakkara, A.; Challacombe, M.; Gill, P. M. W.; Johnson, B.; Chen, W.; Wong, M. W.; Gonzalez, C.; Pople, J. A.; Gaussian 03, revision D.01; Gaussian, Inc.: Wallingford CT, 2004

Cartesian coordinates

0 1				
C	-0.33715100	-2.27630300	0.00004700	
C	-1.29810800	-1.29032900	-0.00004000	
C	-0.70169200	0.00556300	-0.00010700	
C	0.70169200	-0.00556300	-0.00010700	
H	-0.48850500	-3.35578800	0.00002100	
H	-2.37108800	-1.49153700	-0.00007300	
C	1.29810800	1.29032900	-0.00004000	
H	2.37108800	1.49153700	-0.00007300	

C	0.33715100	2.27630300	0.00004700
H	0.48850500	3.35578800	0.00002100
S	-1.29810800	1.64734400	0.00004100
S	1.29810800	-1.64734400	0.00004100

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 9 10 1.0 11 1.0
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0 1			
C	-1.93787500	0.74759900	-0.00001900
C	-0.82573900	1.56128000	-0.00004600
C	0.36515200	0.77675900	-0.00000500
C	0.15605200	-0.61584200	0.00006000
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H	-0.87554100	2.65234700	-0.00008700
C	1.42191500	-1.26778400	0.00004200
H	1.63194000	-2.33571500	0.00005900
C	2.37059700	-0.25173600	-0.00004400
H	3.45773400	-0.31020400	-0.00006000
S	-1.55302700	-0.96801000	0.00006000
N	1.73108900	0.97853800	-0.00011400
H	2.20045100	1.87854100	0.00000700

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 12 13 1.0
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C	0.16300800	-0.62575500	-0.00028000
H	-2.96363000	1.04986500	0.00023800
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H	1.71200000	-2.29653400	0.00003700
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O	1.70616400	1.03944500	-0.00036900
S	-1.54065200	-0.97434700	0.00002700

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9 10 1.0 11 1.0
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C -1.74223500 -0.70063000 -0.00004600
C -0.65689000 0.23373000 0.00023000
C 0.65689000 -0.23373000 0.00023000
H -2.11071700 -2.86699100 -0.00102500
H -2.78945200 -0.37992800 0.00005700
C 1.74223500 0.70063000 -0.00004600
H 2.78945200 0.37992800 0.00005700
C 1.41034000 2.03064600 -0.00015900
H 2.11071700 2.86699100 -0.00102500
Te 0.65689000 -2.33949500 0.00001600
Te -0.65689000 2.33949500 0.00001600

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H 1.14550800 -2.68356400 0.00102900
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H 3.64748400 -1.81351400 0.00074700
S 2.88682400 0.53561700 -0.00033900
Te -1.55932900 -0.29792300 -0.00010300

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C 0.58039700 0.34956900 -0.00060600
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H 2.81079300 0.04644200 -0.00056200
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O 0.58039700 2.73738200 1.28498800
O -0.58006700 -2.73873700 -1.28432400
O -0.58039700 -2.73738200 1.28498800

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O 2.20327700 -0.65767100 1.28238800
S -2.54220500 0.51827400 0.00002300

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C 0.65425200 -0.23849400 -0.00084300
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Se 0.65425200 -2.15910000 0.00009500
Se -0.65425200 2.15910000 0.00009500

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H 3.36331600 -1.66915400 0.00029200
Se -1.72818500 -0.45404200 0.00003400
S 2.48442200 0.63945900 0.00007300

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C	-0.01431300	-0.67978700	-0.00024800
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H	1.66338400	-2.21010700	0.00013400
C	2.11281200	-0.03805200	0.00043600
H	3.19780600	0.04845000	0.00074400
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H	1.66818700	2.05532100	-0.00097800
O	-1.30135100	-1.15324200	-0.00027400

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C	-0.01065200	2.07997600	-0.00027000
C	1.15411100	1.34019300	-0.00002600
C	0.68951600	-0.00725300	-0.00000200
C	-0.68951600	0.00725300	-0.00000200
H	-0.19745000	3.15094300	-0.00068300
H	2.16868100	1.73291700	-0.00011600
C	-1.15411100	-1.34019300	-0.00002600
H	-2.16868100	-1.73291700	-0.00011600
C	0.01065200	-2.07997600	-0.00027000
H	0.19745000	-3.15094300	-0.00068300
O	1.15411100	-1.29206700	0.00032300
O	-1.15411100	1.29206700	0.00032300

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C	-1.71888400	1.26312200	-0.00035700
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C	0.41021900	0.57276000	0.00062200
C	-0.41021900	-0.57276000	0.00062200
H	-2.65801700	1.81376400	-0.00103200
H	-0.11494500	2.78640100	-0.00037200

C	0.41021900	-1.73833200	-0.00014400
H	0.11494500	-2.78640100	-0.00037200
C	1.71888400	-1.26312200	-0.00035700
H	2.65801700	-1.81376400	-0.00103200
N	1.71900700	0.12726500	0.00017800
H	2.55099300	0.70694500	-0.00056400
N	-1.71900700	-0.12726500	0.00017800
H	-2.55099300	-0.70694500	-0.00056400

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